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Preliminary Results for RM3 Co-Design and Structured Innovation

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Abstract

The reference model project was an effort to benchmark the performance and cost of six different marine energy converters, also resulting in a methodology for design and analysis of wave energy converters (WECs). In this study we revisit the well-used RM3 WEC and derive a model considering the relevant dynamics from wave to wire and how those dynamic drivers impact cost using control co-design methods. This model can readily be used for gradient based optimization, borrows a lot of code from WecOptTool, and provides a quantitatively robust means of highlighting pathways for performance improvements. Herein, the quantitative framework for this analysis is presented and preliminary results are described. Future work will extend this to a WecOptTool time domain analysis to respect state constraints and will couple the study with structured innovation approaches to arrive at component-level descriptions of an optimized WEC of a given archetype.

Keywords: Linear WEC control co-design; generator cost model; cost optimization

1. Introduction

The reference model project [1] (RMP) was an effort to benchmark the performance and cost of six different marine energy converters which started more than a decade ago. One outcome was a methodology for design and analysis of the different marine energy converter technologies. Recommended design practices more likely to arrive at an optimally-performing wave energy converter (WEC) have evolved significantly in the intervening years. This includes considering bidirectional power flow from wave to wire (with power take off (PTO) dynamics), optimizing for a useable form of power with the active control by employing realistic PTO efficiency models, and avoiding a sequential approach in making design decisions to avoid limiting the design space early on [2]–[4]. This design approach, known as WEC control co-design, and performed using WecOptTool (<https://github.com/sandialabs/WecOptTool>), concurrently adjusts device hydrodynamic properties, PTO dynamics, and controller that will allow the collective system to attain optimal performance. Thus far, this methodology has been restricted to the maximization of electrical power capture, but, by incorporating parameter cost (in \$) models, can be equivalently applied to LCOE, wherein additional structured innovation techniques (i.e., TRIZ [5]) will be applied to translate the optimal design parameters into a realizable, component-level design.

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1.1. Motivation

The RM3 is to this date one of the most used WEC to study and compare the levelized cost of energy of WECs. Mendoza et al. found that the RM3 power-to-cost ratio hinders its techno-economical viability using a technology performance level assessment [6]. Recently, the RM3 has been used in levelized cost of energy (LCOE) optimization study [7]. McCabe et al. found that LCOE is mostly sensitive to site and economic parameters, rather than geometric and material parameters, when using conventional WEC simulation and control methods, i.e. not considering PTO dynamics and applying control damping only. We revisit the RM3 design using wecOptTool to concurrently design hull geometry, PTO parameters, and controls (the analytical framework for which is presented here), and structured innovation techniques to provide (in future work) a concept-to-component demonstration of WEC co-design.

2. Methodology

The objective of this section is to derive a parameterized model to capture all the interacting dynamics from wave to wire and cost (in \$) models for critical parameters. For simplicity, we would like to equip the RM3 concept with a directly driven rotational PTO, instead of a hydraulic PTO, because of the direct drive PTOs high controllability and ability to provide reactive power to the WEC.

2.1. WEC frequency domain model

The two degree of freedom (DOF) heave velocity \mathbf{U} dynamics in WecOptTool force direction convention are,

$$\mathbf{Z}_i(\omega)\mathbf{U}(\omega) = \mathbf{F}_{ex}(\omega) + \mathbf{F}_{pto}(\omega). \quad (1)$$

With the intrinsic (hydrodynamic) impedance matrix \mathbf{Z}_i and the excitation force vector \mathbf{F}_{ex} and the PTO force vector \mathbf{F}_{pto} . In the following, the frequency dependency (ω) with its N_f components will be dropped for brevity. The PTO has only a single degree of freedom (DOF) and for power transfer between WEC and PTO the relative motion ΔU with kinematics matrix $\mathbf{K} = [1, -1]$ is needed. To consider the impedance observed at the PTO we consider a force exerted by the PTO [8],

$$\Delta U = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{Z}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{F}_{pto}) = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{Y}_i(\mathbf{F}_{pto}). \quad (2)$$

The force f_p acts in the PTO DOF and the resulting force in the two-body WEC frame acts equal-and-oppositely on each connected body as $\mathbf{F}_{pto} = \mathbf{K}^T f_p$.

$$\Delta U = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{Y}_i\mathbf{K}^T f_p \Leftrightarrow \underbrace{(\mathbf{K}\mathbf{Y}_i\mathbf{K}^T)^{-1}}_{Z_{eq}} \Delta U = f_p \quad (3)$$

For now, we neglect the interaction of scattering effects between the two bodies and approximate the relative excitation as the difference between the respective bodies' complex excitation forces $f_{ex,eq} = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{F}_{ex}$ and add this to (3),

$$Z_{eq}\Delta U = f_{ex,eq} + f_p. \quad (4)$$

2.2. Adding drive train frequency domain model

Next, we assume that the rotational PTO is rigidly connected to the WEC translational relative motion with gear ratio N and $f_p = NT_p$ relating the PTO force and its proportional torque. The rotational dynamics obey

$$Z_d\Omega = T_p + T_e. \quad (5)$$

Here, $Z_d = j\omega M_d + B_d + \frac{1}{J_d}K_d$ denotes the drivetrain impedance characterized by the inertia M_d , friction B_d , and rotational spring stiffness $\frac{J_d}{K_d}$ and models drivetrain losses and dynamics. To follow conservation of energy for idealized energy transfer from rotational velocity Ω to translational PTO velocity, $\Omega = -N\Delta U$. Isolating (5) after T_p and inserting the linear-to-rotary relation into (4) yields

$$(Z_{eq} + N^2 Z_d)\Delta U = f_{ex,eq} - NT_e. \quad (6)$$

Combining this with (4), (6) includes both drivetrain dynamics and WEC dynamics: by convention, the generator electromagnetic torque T_e opposes the excitation from the wave to capture energy.

2.3. Adding generator frequency domain model

The generator contains more relevant dynamics that need to be considered for the overall power flow. We assume a linear power invariant for the permanent magnet synchronous motor [9] and two-port modeling techniques [10] (Figure 1) to model the ideal gyrating energy transduction from rotational power to electrical power and include generator losses and dynamics with the winding impedance $Z_w = j\omega L_w + R_w$, characterized by the winding inductance L_w and winding resistance R_w . The entire WEC-PTO and load equivalent circuit is illustrated in Fig. 1. The back-electromagnetic voltage is $V_{bmf} = k_v \Omega = -k_v N \Delta U$, with the motor voltage constant k_v and the electromagnetic torque is given by $T_e = k_\tau I$ as function of torque constant k_τ and current I .

Figure 1: RM3-WEC with PTO represented as two-port system.

The overall dynamic model in two-port form is thus

$$\begin{pmatrix} f_{ex,eq} \\ V_L \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Z_{eq} + N^2 Z_d & Nk_\tau \\ -Nk_v & Z_w \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta U \\ I \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

2.4. Electrical power in the frequency domain

The electrical power captured at the load is

$$P_e = V_L I_L = Z_L I_L^2 = \frac{1}{2} \Re(Z_L) |I|^2. \quad (8)$$

Where $V_L = -Z_L I$ denotes the load voltage resulting from the load impedance $Z_L = j\omega L_L + R_L + \frac{1}{i\omega} C_L$, characterized by the load inductance L_L , resistance R_L , and capacitance C_L , respectively. Please note that with the chosen load structure impedance a PID controller is emulated (with inductance acting as the derivative gain, resistance the proportional gain, and capacitance the integral gain). We can now use (7) to derive an overall impedance from wave excitation to PTO current (wave to wire):

$$-Z_L I = -Nk_v \Delta U + Z_w I \rightarrow \Delta U = \frac{Z_L + Z_w}{Nk_v} I, \text{ insert into the first equation in (7) yields,} \quad (9)$$

$$f_{ex,eq} = \left(\frac{(Z_{eq} + N^2 Z_d)(Z_L + Z_w)}{Nk_v} + Nk_\tau \right) I = Z_{tot} I, \quad (10)$$

The electric power in terms of the individual components' impedances and the equivalent excitation force is

$$P_e(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} R_L \left| \frac{Nk_V}{(Z_{eq} + N^2 Z_d)(Z_W + Z_L) + N^2 k_V k_\tau} f_{ex,eq} \right|^2, \quad (11)$$

and the average power is given by,

$$\bar{P}_e = \sum_{\omega} P_e(\omega). \quad (12)$$

This can generalize to an annual power capture summing over all bins of occurring sea states [2] multiplied with their proportion of occurrence w_i where $\sum_i w_i = 1$.

$$P_e^{ann} = \sum_i (w_i \bar{P}_e(f_{ex,eq,i})) \quad (13)$$

2.5. Cost model

The cost (in \$) model here considers only capital costs affected by parameters varied above: for now, we assume that the operational costs are independent. In this example, three components of material cost are considered the steel used in the WEC hull construction, the copper in the generator windings, and the permanent magnets in the generator, denoted as C_{st} , C_{cu} , and C_{pm} , respectively. The generator cost model considers overall weight and the ratio between permanent magnets and copper. While we do not presume a specific generator in the dynamic analysis, cost data from the SIEMENS 1FW3 complete torque motors from the catalog [11] were used to inform this model. The 1FW3 are water-cooled, high-pole (slow running) permanent-magnet synchronous machines (PMSM and represent an archetype of generators likely suitable for use on the RM3. Key generator parameters are related visualized in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: PMSM catalog parameters and fitted functions.

There is a clear linear trend between generator rated power P_r and generator weight and to a lesser extent between torque constant and weight $W_{gen}(k_\tau, P_r)$, illustrated in the left of Fig 2. The developer does not directly publish cost data or material composition. Instead, we will approximate the ratio between permanent magnets and copper, based on the generators' torque constant. Generally, a high torque constant (force per ampere) requires more permanent magnet material, up to a third of the weight for the maximal torque constants. Ratios found in the literature range from 1:5 up to 1:2 [12] and the ratio function models this based on k_τ .

$$r_{cu-pm}(k_\tau) = 0.2 + \frac{0.1}{25} k_\tau \quad (14)$$

$$C_{gen}(k_\tau, P_r) = (r_{cu-pm}(k_\tau)C_{pm} + (1 - r_{cu-pm})C_{cu})W_{gen}(k_\tau, P_r) \quad (15)$$

The total system cost is then

$$C_{tot}(k_\tau, P_r, A_{RM3}) = C_{gen}(k_\tau, P_r) + A_{RM3} t_{st} C_{st}. \quad (16)$$

With the steel surface area A_{RM3} , which will depend on the simulated geometry and the constant steel thickness t_{st} . Other studies assumed a fixed PTO cost ratio of 20% [13], our model will be able to compare under what circumstances this assumption holds. The annual power to cost ratio is then

$$P_\$ = P_e^{ann} / C_{tot}. \quad (17)$$

3. Optimization

A simplified optimization for a constant geometry RM3 was performed to validate the relationships in Section 2. The optimization is constrained to realistically attainable values. For instance, the generator moment of inertia will be used as lower bound for the drivetrain inertia M_d , but this total inertia can be greater, if for instance, a flywheel is desirable. The optimization problem is

$$\min J(N, k_\tau, R_w, M_d, B_d, K_d, L_L, R_L, C_L) = \min J(\mathbf{x}), \quad \text{subject to } \mathbf{x}_{lb} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ub} \quad (18)$$

The objective function $J(\mathbf{x})$ can be either (12), (13), or (17). Here, using a Sequential Least Squares Programming optimizer to minimize (12) results in the following optimized impedances and electrical power for a single irregular sea state ($H_s = 1.67m, T_p = 8.22s$, most occurring representative sea state at PacWave South, processed with MhKit [14] and converted into an excitation force with WecOptTool's waves.py module). Because the default PTO configuration was chosen based on conservative initial engineering judgment, too much significance should not be ascribed to the increased power capture of the optimal configuration, but what is notable is how the shape of the optimal impedance is fundamentally different from the default particularly over frequency bands with significant relative excitation.

Figure 3: System dynamics and electrical power for initial guess system and system optimized for average electrical power.

4. Future Work

To expand on the presented example, alterations the RM3 geometry can be iterated as an outer loop around (18), such that an optimal geometry (along with its optimal PTO and controller configuration) can be found for a set of sea-states. Utilizing (17) as the objective functions with expanded and enhanced cost models will suggest LCOE optimal configurations. Contrasting these suggestions with power-optimal configurations suggested by (12) will highlight areas of design and contradictions/trade-offs for which innovative approaches would be particularly beneficial to LCOE. Applying structured innovation while these efforts are contributing to the achievement of a WEC configuration demonstrably optimal within a robust mathematical framework will combine contemporary best practices into a highly useful example reference model.

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References

- [1] V. S. Neary *et al.*, "Methodology for Design and Economic Analysis of Marine Energy Conversion (MEC) Technologies," Mar. 2014.
- [2] C. A. M. Ströfer, D. T. Gaebele, R. G. Coe, and G. Bacelli, "Control Co-Design of Power Take-off Systems for Wave Energy Converters using WecOptTool," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, pp. 1–11, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2023.3272868.
- [3] G. Bacelli and R. G. Coe, "A control co-optimization approach for the design of wave energy converter power take-offs," xx-xx 2022.
- [4] G. Bacelli and R. G. Coe, "Comments on Control of Wave Energy Converters," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 478–481, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TCST.2020.2965916.
- [5] Y. Salamatov, "TRIZ: THE RIGHT SOLUTION AT THE RIGHT TIME: A Guide to Innovative Problem Solving".
- [6] N. Mendoza *et al.*, "Developing technology performance level assessments for early-stage wave energy converter technologies," 2021.
- [7] R. McCabe, O. Murphy, and M. Haji, "Multidisciplinary Optimization to Reduce Cost and Power Variation of a Wave Energy Converter," in *Volume 3A: 48th Design Automation Conference (DAC)*, St. Louis, Missouri, USA: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Aug. 2022, p. V03AT03A023. doi: 10.1115/DETC2022-90227.
- [8] A. Hamilton, F. Cazenave, D. Forbush, R. G. Coe, and G. Bacelli, "The MBARI-WEC: a power source for ocean sensing," *J. Ocean Eng. Mar. Energy*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 189–200, May 2021, doi: 10.1007/s40722-021-00197-9.
- [9] R. Coe, G. Bacelli, S. Spencer, D. Forbush, and K. Dullea, "MASK3 for Advanced WEC Dynamics and Controls." Marine and Hydrokinetic Data Repository (MHKDR); Sandia National Laboratories, p. 4 files, 2019. doi: 10.15473/1581762.
- [10] D. C. Karnopp, D. L. Margolis, and R. C. Rosenberg, *System Dynamics: Modeling, Simulation, and Control of Mechatronic Systems*. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.
- [11] Siemens AG, "SINAMICS Configuration Manual · 07/2011 1FW3 complete torque motors." Jul. 2011. Accessed: Aug. 15, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://cache.industry.siemens.com/dl/files/103/51670103/att_111084/v1/1FW3_en-US.pdf
- [12] F. K. Moghadam and A. R. Nejad, "Evaluation of PMSG-based drivetrain technologies for 10-MW floating offshore wind turbines: Pros and cons in a life cycle perspective," *Wind Energy*, vol. 23, no. 7, pp. 1542–1563, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1002/we.2499.
- [13] Y. Peña-Sanchez, D. García-Violini, and J. V. Ringwood, "Control co-design of power take-off parameters for wave energy systems," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 55, no. 27, pp. 311–316, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2022.10.531.
- [14] rpaul18 *et al.*, "MHKiT-Software/MHKiT-Python: v0.7.0." Zenodo, Aug. 11, 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8239960.

